

Understanding the Teacher's Beliefs and Perceptions in ICT Integration for Effective Classroom Teaching in Higher Education

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Abstract

Beliefs are deeply ingrained mental tendencies that guide our actions and persist over time. Perceptions, however, are shaped by our direct experiences with the world at specific moments. Additionally, what teachers believe is influenced by their past experiences. Teachers' beliefs often impact their future ICT integration practices. Teachers with positive beliefs about technology have long recognized and accepted it as an essential factor for effective ICT use in classroom teaching. This study aims to understand the opinions and experiences of high school teachers regarding the integration of ICT for effective classroom teaching. Our study employed a quantitative approach aligned with a survey design because it is cost-effective, less time-consuming, and capable of capturing data from a larger sample at once.

The survey questionnaire was used to collect data from 210 high school teachers across different locations in Nepal. All ethical considerations, including anonymity, respondent consent, data security, and voluntary participation, were addressed during the research process. Descriptive statistics were used to analyze the collected data. We applied the Factor Reduction Method to explore the relationships between different survey instruments and to generate Principal Components. Our data analysis initially involved Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and subsequently included Logistic Regression Analysis to examine the association between independent and dependent variables. Our results suggest a positive association between professional development in ICT, access to ICT resources and infrastructure, leadership support, and school culture regarding ICT, as well as teachers' Beliefs and perceptions of ICT Integration for effective classroom teaching in high school education.

Keywords: *effective classroom teaching, high school education, teachers' beliefs, technology*